

A Milestone in Nader Ale Ebrahim's Academic Career

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Abstract

I have received 1,527 citations from 1,430 documents to 48 publications in the SCOPUS database up to the end of the year 2022 (The list extracted from SCOPUS on January 5th, 2023). I know it is not a big number compared to others in the field, but it is a small milestone in my academic career. I am grateful because I could have never dreamed of being where I am today. Thanks to all my co-authors who have published with me over the years. It was great writing articles with you as an attempt to disseminate knowledge. Thank you to all respective researchers, scientists, and individuals for recognizing our research team's work. Once more, I would like to say huge thanks to all my fantastic co-authors and all of you who read and cited our papers. Thank you very much for your recognition, encouragement, and support. Your citations will provide more evidence and inspire more researchers in the field to continue conducting more research. The citation number can be considered as one of the indicators for the impacts of our studies on the academic community and I am happy to see the impacts. It has been a challenging, but rewarding, journey with its ups & its downs, which I have loved overall. Once again, I am thankful to all of those who have supported me on my academic journey. It is indeed a special milestone that I will never forget. I hope the new year brings more exciting research and more collaboration between researchers in the field.

Keywords: Research Tools, Research Impact, Research Visibility, Bibliometrics, University Rankings, Technology Management, Virtual R&D teams.

About Nader Ale Ebrahim

[Nader Ale Ebrahim](#) currently works as a “Research Visibility and Impact” freelancer consultant. Nader is also an adjunct lecturer at Alzahra University. He was working as a visiting research fellow with the Institute of Management and Research Services (IPPP), at the University of Malaya from 2013 to November 2017. Nader holds a Ph.D. in Technology Management from the Faculty of Engineering, [University of Malaya](#). He has over 25 years of experience in the field of technology management and new product development in different companies. His current research interests are University rankings, Open Access, Research visibility, [Research Tools](#), and Bibliometrics. Dr. Nader provides assistance and guidance for researchers in disseminating and promoting their research work to enhance their research visibility and impact and citations. He believes that the research cycle does not end with publications alone, thus he encourages pro-activeness in the dissemination of research outputs.

Nader is well-known as the creator of the “[Research Tools](#)” Box. Dr. Nader was the winner of the Refer-a-Colleague Competition and has received prizes from renowned establishments such as Thomson Reuters (recently, known as Clarivate Analytics). He has so far conducted over 400 workshops around the world. Nader has published over 100 peer-reviewed conference papers and journal articles, in addition to three chapters in books. His publications have received over 4500 citations in Google Scholar (h-index = 29).

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